

Effect of Assimilating the concept of “Public Marginal Cost” on “Environmental Protection”

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Abstract:

Background:

It's beyond commonsense that every citizen shall be vigilant enough to ensure that every rupee spent from Public Funds, the Treasury as received in the name of 'exchequer' should be an asset to the Society. On the other hand, to every rupee spent from exchequer, it should also be ensured to the extent that whether such a spending could be avoided or otherwise, the exorbitant spending is judiciously checked. Voluntary environment protection by each and every individual to multinational companies in India, adhering to the Environmental Laws in perfect order would result in reduction of cost by the exchequer both through the protection of Nature as well as through improved Health of the public at large. Here, Environmental Protection is broadly considered beyond Nature's environment, though it's a primary concern in this study. The broad consideration include judicious use of each and every resource, including currency (any amount as received by exchequer), as GDP & GNI are interchangeably understandable.

Environmental protection is the practice of protecting the natural environment by individuals, groups and governments.¹ Its objectives are to conserve natural resources and the existing natural environment and, where possible, to repair damage and reverse trends.² Due to the pressures of over consumption, population growth and technology, the biophysical environment is being degraded, sometimes permanently. This has been recognized, and governments have begun placing restraints on activities that cause environmental degradation. Since the 1960s, environmental movements have created more awareness of the multiple environmental problems. There is disagreement on the extent of the environmental impact of human activity, so protection measures are occasionally debated.

Any misappropriation, unwanted projects, all results in Resource Depletion, which is already scarce and adds to Environmental Degradation. Hence, it's considered Broad.

Recent exorbitant spending on AI Camera installation is of late questioned by the Hon. High Court. In spite of Statutory Audit, which is an inevitable part of Governance ending at Comptroller and Audit General of India, extravagance and corruption becomes part of the game. The CAG is also the statutory auditor of the Lokpal.³

Young generation, the students in particular, shall contribute a lot to the society primarily through propagating it's awareness, or through public litigation at times of need.

Aim: To find the effect of Assimilating the concept of “Public Marginal Cost” on “Environmental Protection”.

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3. "India Code: Section Details". www.indiacode.nic.in. Retrieved 26 May 2023.
4. [The objectives, findings & conclusion are summarised in page, 7]

Introduction:

Ensure that necessary Cognitive awareness is built in every citizen so that our Nation is a safe space for future generations to live-in through sustainable development & a pollution free place without adding any burden to the exchequer, hence is this humble effort.

Indian environmental law concerns the law and policy of India concerning the protection of the environment, measures taken to reverse climate change and achieve a zero carbon economy. Since the sixties concern over the state of environment has grown the world over.

Water (Prevention And Control Of Pollution) Cess Act, 1974. Air (Prevention And Control Of Pollution) Act, 1977. Forest Conservation Act, 1980. Environmental Protection Act, 1986, are few among them, to that effect.^[4]

Be economically safe would mean a homeostasis as far as Expenditure & Revenue have synchronization in a holistic view with every activity involved throughout the life. While sufficient buffer might act as a cushion to meet the Disasters, a seldom extravaganza should be anticipated to upkeep the Esteem and unforeseen expenses without wheezing. It's applicable not alone to Individuals, but to any Society or the Nation itself.

Most of the time, to 3rd world Nations in particular, the unsound day-to-day affairs ends up in deficit budgets negatively oozing out the stringent revenue which already failed to meet targets and never lead to a surplus.

The Real Income concept in Economics (in short; foreseeing inflation) always focus on meeting the specified target in spite of an anticipated inflation and haphazard management to nullify the negativity running out of it. While inflation is healthy to some extent and the market forces can't rectify the same by itself, individuals are forced to adjust with their budgets.

But the haphazard management of treasury of the exchequer not alone by the Governance, but by every member of human specie either by recklessly careless attitude of the former OR by the irresponsible attitude-behavior link by the later, the economy collapses by itself and no sustenance of the ecology itself is possible, in future.

The discussion brought forward here would awaken the thoughts in the reader more about importance of creating awareness in the concept of Real Income and its attainment in umpteen ways through Public Attitude & Behavior.

This work tend to introduce a new concept namely, "Public Marginal Cost" and the writer wish to state that a true assimilation of this concept by public at large right from nurturing in the beginning of the life of an offspring, a strong attitude-behavior link can be developed and homeostasis at every level of Health as envisaged by WHO, viz. Physical, Mental & Social would be possible and also its sustenance. The covenants so arrived in each mind shall be adhered by one and all from within as an entity.

To this part of the world, "Bharatha", Environment is not a new concept as every Plant, tree, every specie was treated as gift of God and Human beings always used to respect them.

Nature has gifted us with variety of foods for us to consume and stay healthy. While food basically meant to provide energy for accomplishment of tasks, the basis of life was well known to people from time immemorial that protection of plants, water & earth which provided food for both flora & fauna.

<https://www.legalserviceindia.com/legal/topic-32-environmental-law.html>

Forests in ancient India were an integral part of people's lives. The Aryan and Dravidian civilizations lived in harmony with the forests and their wildlife. As worshippers of nature, they preferred to live in sylvan (associated with woods) settings and inspiring landscapes.

The Vedas, the Upanishads and the Puranas reveal the vital role of forests and forestry during those ancient days. The two great epics of the Vedic

period, Ramayana and Mahabharata mention forests and woodlands like Chitrakotta, Dandakaranya, Nandanavana and Khandavarana. Apart from these naturally growing forests, there is mention of artificial forests such as Amaravana, Khadivana, Devadaravana, Shirishavana and Osadhivana. This sylvan life made him 'Swastha'

i.e. a state of both physical & mental comfort. [5]

It was well delineated by Mahatma Gandhi century back that it is the Sustenance that was important and not Abundance.

He insisted people to live Eco-friendly by weaving own cloth, cultivate by ourselves and treat the illness by using our own herbs. Everything was there in Nature, self-endowed.

Advancement of technology paved way for 'Economies of Scale' which produced multi-fold, provided plenty for human beings to live at ease & comfort.

But we failed to understand the untapped energy of fossil fuel when tapped, mixed with Oxygen and other factors of production its Negative Economic costs like Carbon Dioxide, Carbon Monoxide, Methane, Lead, many Nitrates and innumerable other toxins overthrew value of Economic goods produced by it.

When development of science gave way to hitherto experiences and beliefs about environment, over dependence on environment and its over exploitation resulted in Natural Disasters, finally at least few stand recognized the need for a 're-birth' of neutral dependence on gifts of nature, the necessity to replenish the stock of more than what gets depleted due to human action. Certainly, it is a welcoming move.

A good portion of this work is meant to improve the cognition of the readers, as knowledge in any subject is the primary criteria for understanding. Hence an in-depth discussion about Marginal Social Cost, Marginal Private Cost, Marginal External Cost, Opportunity Cost etc. are well delineated with sufficient explanation to every concept. [page, 5]

Taking into consideration the whole activity involved to educate public at large towards Environmental Protection, Ecological behavior, Attitudinal change etc., an assimilable new concept, Public Marginal Cost [page, 4] is well defined with a view to inculcate a culture of thought in every citizen towards Environmental Protection.

Learning and Assimilation of a concept plays a very important role in behavioral change.

A simple learning that, if there is only one child in a house, to get him to school, the family may need only one water bottle but if the family has 5 children, naturally the family would need 5 water bottles. The Marginal External Cost [page, 5] which act as a threat to Environmental Protection can be

understood only if the concept is assimilated.

<https://vsktelangana.org/environment-conservation-in-ancient-india>

Similarly, just spitting on road, might result in outbreak of an epidemic! Here, the concept of Marginal External Cost [Page, 5] by definition may fail to explain the burden suffered by exchequer due to above sociopathic behavior.

To explain the cost incurred to exchequer due to negligence in quality control of a Common Property Resource, a Bridge, which collapses in 3 years, which otherwise would have served the nation and its population for more than 300 years, the concept of Marginal External Cost is insufficient.

Man-made disasters can include hazardous material spills, fires, groundwater contamination, transportation accidents, structure failures, mining accidents, explosions and acts of terrorism.

Hazardous materials are chemicals that if accidentally released can cause damage to the environment and health. Many chemicals used in industry, agriculture, medical research, and in our homes can become hazardous if not properly used. Many hazardous materials are transported by rail or road and can be subject to accidental release.

The concept: Public Marginal Cost

Public Marginal Cost: Definition

“Public Marginal Cost” is that part of expenditure expected to be expended by the exchequer to compensate the damages caused by either ignorance by general public, greed or due to sociopathic intention, to reduce Marginal Private Cost [1] on the part of individual to multinational including the one caused by nature's wrath

Few examples that result in Public Marginal Cost:

#The least by spitting of public, thereby resultant contagious disease

#Lack of hygiene, thereby resultant contagious disease,

#A fatal Police Action on an accused.

#Man-made disasters, right from household waste Management onwards

#Inability to prevent, a preventable natural disaster.

#Hazardous chemical disasters

#Public Works failures, resulting from corruption & ignorance

#Terrorism

[1] Marginal Private Cost; as explained under “Other Operational Definitions [Page, 5]”.

Materials and Methods: Environmental Attitude and Ecological Behavior by Florian G. Kaiser, Sybille Wolfing and Urs Fuhrer, data collected through Purposive Sampling.

Other Operational Definitions:

Marginal private cost:

Marginal private cost (MPC) is the change in the producer's total cost brought about by the

production of an additional unit of a good or service. It is also known as marginal cost of production. For example, if production costs rise from \$1,000 to \$1,050 as one more unit of a good is produced, the marginal private cost is \$50.

Marginal Social Cost:

Marginal social cost (MSC) is the change in society's total cost brought about by the production of an additional unit of a good or service. It includes both marginal private cost and marginal external cost.

For example, it costs a producer \$50 to produce an additional unit of a good. Suppose that when an additional unit is produced, pollution is emitted which caused \$25 worth of damage to few square feet area. The marginal social cost of production is the producer's cost plus the external cost, or \$75.

Marginal External Cost:

Marginal external cost (MEC) is the change in the cost to parties other than the producer or buyer of a good or service due to the production of an additional unit of the good or service. For example, it costs the producer \$50 to produce another unit of a good. Suppose this production results in pollution which causes another \$60 worth of damage to another company's plant or society.

Opportunity Cost:

The opportunity cost is the value the individual/organisation or the Nation forgoes when choosing one option over another, whether the loss is monetary or use of time (productivity) or energy (efficiency). When an Organisation decides to allocate resources to one activity or area, it also decides not to pursue a competing activity. Opportunity cost is an especially important calculation for nation like India/3rd world countries, which by definition have more limited resources and funds than their larger counterparts. It involves weighing which decision will potentially provide the greatest return on their investments.

The opportunity cost is time spent studying and that money to spend on something else. A farmer chooses to plant wheat; the opportunity cost is planting a different crop, or an alternate use of the resources (land and farm equipment). A commuter takes the train to work instead of driving, to put it simple.

Statistical Analysis:

Only Descriptive Statistical Analysis and discussions are done to limit the content.

NUMBER OF SAMPLES (done through Deliberate Sampling)

15 deliberate samples each from:

1. Environmental Promotion and Propagation Organisation in Kerala, namely, The Sastra Sahitya Parishad [GROUP-I]

2. Personnel directly involved with small scale Industrial Production Units, Personnel Involved in

Direct Hotel Business & Fish Market [GROUP-II]

GROUP-I [Maximum possible individual score is 30]

Sub-group	SCORES				Tot	Avg
Not Active, Professionals, 4 persons	27	27	28	28	110	27.50
Active, Educated, Salaried, 4 persons	28	29	30	30	117	29.25
Socially Active, Working class, Hard Labour, 4 persons	29	29	30	30	118	29.50
Active, Social Work, Variously engaged, 3 persons	30	30	30		90	30.00
					435	29.063

Out of 30 maximum scores possible, average received from 15 samples is 29.0. This brings few agreements with the theoretical prepositions that when Strong Attitudes are formed through life-style, blended with work-style and area

of activity involved, shaping of behavior takes place. Most importantly there is a strong formation of Concepts in relation to positive Environmental Awareness.

Average Prosocial behavior of Group-I was found to be 7 out of 8.

GROUP-II [Maximum possible individual score is 30]

Sub-group	SCORES				Tot	Avg
Small Scale Industry Owners, 4 persons	13	13	13	15	54	15.50
Distributors of Plastic Industry Products, 4 persons	16	17	17	19	69	17.25
Direct Hotel Business, 4 persons	16	16	19	19	70	17.50
Fish Marketers, 3 persons	19	21	22		62	20.67
					255	17.73

Whereas in this group with same questionnaire, out of 30 maximum scores possible, average received from 15 samples is 18.0. This too brings few agreements with theoretical prepositions that when Strong Attitudes are Not formed through life-style, blended with work-style and area of

activity involved, shaping of behavior took place with more greed ignoring sustainable environmental facilitation. Here, No strong formation of Concepts has taken place in them in relation to positive Environmental Awareness.

Average Prosocial behavior of Group-II was found to be 4 out of 8.

Objectives, its establishment, Hypotheses of this study & Conclusion:

Objectives were,

- i) To enquire whether Assimilation of an Environmental Concept has any influence on Attitude and Ecological Behaviour of a person.
- ii) To find the relationship between Prosocial behaviour and Environmental Attitude.

After having done the Study, as far as objectives are concerned, it is found that:

- i) Scores justify that there is a strong relation between Assimilation of Environmental concept, Attitude and Ecological Behavior of the people, involvement through daily practice of life, profession etc certainly contribute to it.
- ii) Scores justify that there is a strong relation between Prosocial behavior and Environmental Attitude.

Conclusion:

Hence, propagating a new scientific concept, namely, Public Marginal cost right from early Academics should provide for NURTURING a better environmental concept and positive approach to their Ecological behavior.

Submitted to the kindness of the heart of every reader with a request to get enunciated to the terminologies discussed with the essence of its title.

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